

The Ideal Woman: Beauty Contests in Interwar Romania

Sonia-Doris Andraş

Abstract

In the period 1929 – 1936, Romania evolved from a traditional agricultural society to a modern, cosmopolitan and consumerist society. Bucharest, its capital, synthesized these transformations. The ideal of beauty – as reflected in fashion – was subject to the same processes of modernization and commodification. Beauty contests showed how the changing beauty ideals were constructed and promoted in order to fit the requested pattern.

While the ideal Romanian beauty was diversified in the contemporary media, Miss Contests were much stricter, adding restrictive moral criteria to the physical requirements.¹ Aesthetically, the ideal woman who could become Miss Romania, and subsequently compete internationally, was closer to the Western-Hollywood type. The published portraits of the participants merged the idyllic, national-based beauty ideal with a host of the Hollywood role models: the siren, the vamp, the innocent, the glamorous, the voluptuous and the intelligent.

My paper focuses on the official Miss Romania – Europe / Universe contests between 1929 with the first such official event and 1936 when they were cancelled due to the imminent war. Embedded in the Fashion Studies and Gender Studies, my research investigates the relevant interwar Romanian magazines, journals, fiction and non-fiction literature in order to identify and interpret the Interwar ideals of beauty in Romania and Bucharest. It explores the intricate mechanisms of gender relations, the role and position of women in Interwar Romania, as filtered through the pursuit and glorification of beauty.

In conclusion, the ideal of female beauty in Interwar Romania was a complex phenomenon, encapsulating the social, political and historical issues, that were at times converging and at other times were dissonant. These issues, however, managed to blend together and coexisted in the multicultural Romania of that period.

Key Words: Beauty, fashion, Romania, interwar, Bucharest, beauty contests, beauty pageants, beauty ideals

Interwar Romania evolved from a traditional agricultural society to a modern, cosmopolitan and consumerist one. Bucharest, its capital, synthesized these transformations. The Romanian pageant organizers competed in creating modern and relevant events displaying contestants who were close to the ideal woman, proving that their behaviour, morality, social standing are fit for the national and international norms.ⁱⁱ

The ideal of beauty was subject to the process of modernization and commodification, making identities and cultures public, and thus visible. Furthermore, gender norms were perpetuated by the symbolic politicization of the contest.ⁱⁱⁱ This ideal is neither homogenous, nor particular. Even if the rules of entrance, participation and conduct are strict, the actual choice bares the same subjectivity as the idea of beauty itself.^{iv}

Beauty contests have inherited the temporary honouring of a particular person on arbitrary hierarchies, but transformed them to become relevant to a society increasingly democratic, capitalist and scientifically objective.^v Taking the largely anthropological idea of symbolic currency to a capitalist understanding, beauty pageants are described as typical endeavours of mass consumer culture.^{vi}

Aesthetically, the ideal woman to become Miss Romania and compete internationally was closer to the Western-Hollywood type. The published portraits of the participants, however, merged the idyllic, national-based ideal with a host of the Hollywood role models: the siren, the vamp, the innocent, the glamorous, the voluptuous and the intelligent.

Interwar Romania would see numerous types of beauty pageants organized by magazines or press trusts, like *Ilustrațiunea Română*^{vii} (*The Romanian Illustration*^{viii}) and *România Ilustrată* (*The Illustrated Romania*)^{ix}. These rivals organized two *Miss Romania*, with its own international development. For *Realitatea Ilustrată*, *Miss Romania* was followed by *Miss Universe* and for *Ilustrațiunea Română*, by *Miss Europe* and a parallel *Miss Universe*.

The first Romanian participation to *Miss Universe* –Galveston, was in 1929, with Magda Demetrescu, who won sixth place, then in 1930 Mariana Mirică, who finished on the third place. As the Galveston contests were cancelled in 1932, the next *Miss Universe* participation for Romania was in Brussels in 1935, with Dorothee Cristesco.

For *Miss Europe*, the first to participate was Mărioara Gănescu in 1929 (Paris). In 1930 Zoica Dona participated to *Miss Europe* (Cannes, Paris), and to the Rio de Janeiro *Miss Universe* pageant. The next year the Romanian representative was Tanți Vișoreanu (Paris), in 1932 Lilian Delescu (Nice, also received a Ford automobile^x), in 1933 Dina Mihalcea (Madrid) and in 1934 Hélène Dona (Hastings, England).^{xi}

The analysis of beauty contest in Interwar Romania can identify social, political issues and ideals of nationhood. Beyond the aesthetic and emotional elements such events entail, the political dimension is built on feelings of nationalism, in an on-

going game of power.^{xii} A reporter from *Realitatea Ilustrată*^{xiii} accompanies the Romanian group to the 1929 Galveston pageant. The importance given to Miss Universe is visible not only from the cortege of contestants, their chaperones and organizers, but from a myriad of reporters, a marching band and a huge crowd. Apart from Miss Austria, the only other European who received a prize was Magda Demetrescu who received a warm reception by the Romanians in the United States.

The beauty queen becomes the key to an enormous capitalist machine^{xiv}: her participation is possible due to a sponsoring institution: she is crowned, paraded and used to promote different institutions and sell any type of relevant product.

In 1929 the newspaper *Românul (The Romanian)*^{xv} published a meticulous account of Miss Romania's election. The jury had Interior Minister Vaida-Voievod^{xvi} as a patron, and included noted writers, sculptors and intellectual figures. The 72 contestants, the organizers and their entourage paraded through Bucharest's main commercial artery, Victoria Avenue, with 150 automobiles. Miss Romania and becomes the "ambassador of Romanian beauty, who is to represent us across the ocean."

In July, *Realitatea Ilustrată*^{xvii} followed the tour of Miss Universe 1929, Lisl Goldarbeiter in Romania, alongside Demetrescu. This visit is profitable for everybody involved, adding to the advertising potential.

In 1930, *Ilustrațiunea Română*^{xviii} announces the contest for their Miss Romania, who will set on the Paris-Rio de Janeiro trail. The grand prize is 3.300.000 lei.^{xix} The International Committee promises to pay all the winners' travelling expenses to Paris or Rio de Janeiro. The event was public and crowded. The jury included professors, generals, doctors, jurists, writers, journalists and artists. Zoica Dona was elected as Miss Romania 1930 and the magazine publishes an extensive interview with Dona^{xx}. A collage of finalists' portraits is included^{xxi} and an article on her expedition on the Cote d'Azur^{xxii}, where she was received as a celebrity. The event included a contest for the fashion houses.

Realitatea Ilustrată's Miss Romania 1930 is held in Sinaia^{xxiii}. The article features a collage^{xxiv} of the event, from the huge crowds that waited for them in the train station, the contest, the elegant soirees and parades to the Beauty queens. The master of ceremonies is noted Romanian writer Liviu Rebreanu. After hours of deliberations, he announces Miss Romania: Zizi Teodorescu.

The same day, *Ilustrațiunea Română*^{xxv} responds by displaying Zoica Dona on the front cover, with Maurice de Waleffe, the editor-in-chief "from the great daily 'Le Journal'" from Paris and secretary general of the international beauty contest Paris – Rio de Janeiro. They report that Dona posed for a famous Romanian painter, Stoenescu in his workshop on rue Auguste Vacquerie.^{xxvi} *Realitatea Ilustrată* publishes an interview with then Miss Romania, Zizi Teodorescu^{xxvii}.

Ilustrațiunea Română starts 1931 with an issue dedicated to its Miss Romania, Tanți Vișoreanu^{xxviii}. She is featured on both covers and the magazine dedicates four pages to her^{xxix} and a collage of pictures.^{xxx} Like Dona, Vișoreanu is the

daughter of a general. She is a 21 years old brunette, with distinguished features and an „*admirable body*” and “*she generally possesses all the qualities that warrant her to remain not only at a national title’s level, but at world beauty titles alike.*” After serving in the jury, painter Stoenescu exclaims that she has a vaporous beauty emanating from her whole being, and she has “*a supple beauty, full of grace, of charm, something from a gazelle’s walk and the freshness of May flowers.*”^{xxxix}

After the failure of both the attempt for popular vote and a movie the magazine financed, *Parada frumuseții (The Beauty Parade)*, the Miss Romania 1931 returned to a competent jury. In June, *Realitatea Ilustrată* features an interview with Miss Romania 1931, Erastia Peretz.^{xxxix} She is blonde, with green eyes, tall and “*she spreads around her a special charm*” of “*simplicity, of moderation*” along with the “*suave perfume of a bright youthfulness, of glee.*”^{xxxix}

In May 1933, *Ilustrațiunea Română*^{xxxiv} displayed beauty queens on both covers and includes an interview with Dina Mihalcea.^{xxxv} She is blonde, with huge blue eyes, “*with a distinguished appearance, with an admirable body framed by harmonious lines,*” a “*beautiful diction which completes her qualities endowed by nature.*”^{xxxvi} She is athletic, practices gymnastics regularly.^{xxxvii}

The Romanian cultural world was no stranger to beauty queens. Although some deplored shallowness and “Americanization,” thus the extinction of the Romanian natural, bucolic, original beauty, there was a great number of voices that gave this displays of female beauty a great importance. The pageant organizers sought for bringing respected personalities as judges. They would also finance novels and movies^{xxxviii} to popularize these contests. In 1929, I. Doru’s *Regină pentru un an / Queen for a Year*^{xxxix}, documented a fictionalized depiction of the Galveston pageant. Even though the novel did not break any great literary grounds, it was extensively promoted in *Realitatea Ilustrată*.

Pageants are frequently critiqued in intellectual circles as being trivial, therefore with no cultural relevance. The reluctance could be due to the idea that any research on beauty risks to be deemed un-intellectual.^{xl} This has been the basis on which the critique on beauty pageants was built in Interwar Romania and that they debased the Romanian woman.

For example, in 1929, philosopher Constantin Noica mocks Miss Romania and the first Galveston participation as an abhorrent denial of the autochthonous values in favour of foreign shallowness^{xli}. The only reason he sees for her fame is her ephemeral beauty and wonders what will become of her after she ceases to be “*the least ugly among the ugliest.*”^{xlii} In 1929, writer Cezar Petrescu wrote a novel titled *Miss Romania*^{xliii}, where he mocked not only the contestants themselves for being un-cultured at best, but the organizers as well.

The conservative, right-wing, nationalistic press also described beauty pageants in derogatory terms. One of the critiques comes with Goldarbaiter’s visit in

Romania in 1929 and how she let herself be used to be commercialized for an and the fact Miss Romania demeaned herself and her country by accompanying her.^{xliv}

Women can only binarily: either as the lascivious woman who only exists for the pleasure of man-kind, or the potential or actual mother whose primary function, apart from having pleasant looks is to perpetuate the human species.^{xlv} Additionally, the general opposition is not always because of these moral and dogmatic implications, but also for economic reasons.^{xlvi} Also, even male students publicly ask their female counterparts not to participate because beauty should not be a criteria when judging an intellectual.

All in all, the history of beauty pageants cannot be polarized; it is not a simple positive-negative issue. It is a complex subject that will actually lead to a sophisticated paradigm that incorporates both subjectivity and objectivity, the participants and the observers. The research on beauty pageants underlines how unclear the boundaries of understanding and the actual questions are, an idea worthy to be called cultural work by Banet-Wiser.^{xlvii}

The ideal of female beauty in Interwar Romania was a complex phenomenon, encapsulating the social, political and historical issues that were at times converging and at other times dissonant. Although they may be described as morally ambiguous, beauty contests have become an integral part of the international modern experience.

These issues, however, managed to blend together and coexisted in multicultural Romania. Beauty pageants have evolved in time, yet they still hold on to the basic principle: the quantification of beauty and judgement by a subjective yet impartial jury. Similarly, the emotional intensity has permeated to the very core of the Romanian psyche.

Bibliography

‘Alegerea „Miss României”. Grandioasa manifestație pentru „Miss Arad”’ (‘The Election of Miss Romania.’ The Grand Manifestation for “Miss Arad”) in *Românul – Organ al Partidului Național Țărănesc Român Arad (The Romanian – Agency of the Romanian National Peasants’ Party Arad)* 13, 24 (March 1929): 2.

A.M., ‘Epilogul concursului de frumusețe mondial. Frumusețea feminină ca mijloc de speculă; d-ra Goldarbeiter se arată pentru bani’ (‘The Epilogue of the World Beauty Contest. Female Beauty as a Means of Profit; Miss Goldarbeiter Shows Up For Money’) *Clujul* 29-35 (8 September 1929): 1.

Banet-Weiser, S., *The Most Beautiful Girl in the World. Beauty Pageants and National Identity* (Berkeley, Los Angeles and London: University of California Press, 1999).

Ballerino Cohen, C. Richard Wilk and Beverly Stoeltje, *Beauty Queens on the Global Stage. Gender, Contests and Power* (New York and London: Routledge, 1996).

Christesco, Dorothée, *La fortune d’Alexandre Manzoni en France. Origine du théâtre et du roman romantiques* (Paris: Editions Balzac, 1943).

Christescu, Dorothea, *Parisul lor ... momente din vremea domnilor in uniforme verzi (Their Paris... Moments from the Time of the Gentlemen in Green Uniforms)* (București, Universul, 1944).

Doru, I. *Regină pentru un an. Romanul unui concurs de frumusețe – Miss Romania – Miss Universe (Queen for a Year. The Novel of a Beauty Contest – Miss Romania – Miss Universe)* (Bucharest: N/A).

Fardon, R., *Power and Knowledge: Anthropological and Sociological Approaches* (Edinburgh: Scottish Intellectual and high culture Press, 1986).

Cu ce hrănim lumea! (With What Are We Feeding the World!), Cultura poporului (The People’s Culture) Bucharest, X. 309 (26 January 1930): 1.

‘Știri’ (‘News’), *Foaia diecezană. Organul eparhiei ortodoxe române a Caransebeșului (The Diocesan Paper. The Organ of the Orthodox Diocese of Caransebeș)* 6 (7 February 1932): 7.

Foley, B., *Undressed for Success. Beauty Contestants and Exotic Dancers as Merchants of Morality* (New York and Basingstoke, Hampshire: Palgrave Macmillan, 2005).

Fussu, V., ‘Să fie oare așa?’ (‘Is it Really So?’), *Cultura poporului (The People’s Culture)*, Bucharest, X. 309 (26 January 1930): 1.

Ilustrațiunea Română 1925-1937.

Marwick, A., *It. A History of Human Beauty* (London and New York: Hambledon and London, 2004).

Noica, C., *Semnele Minervei. Publicistica, I. 1927-1929 (The Signs of Minerva. Publishing, I. 1927-1929)* (Bucharest: Humanitas, 1994).

Peretz, Erastia, *Ceai dansant (The Dansant)* (București: Vreemea, n. y.).

Peretz, Erastia, *Stele căzătoare (Falling Stars)* (București: Cugetarea, 1946).

Peretz, Erastia, *La cuisine roumaine* (Paris, Les Editions du Jour, 1979).

Petrescu, C., *Miss Romania* in Cezar Petrescu, *La paradis general - Miss Romania (At General Paradise – Miss Romania)* (second edition, Bucharest: Cartea Romaneasca, 1970), 287-537.

Pontynen, A., *For the Love of Beauty. Art, History, and the Moral Foundations of Aesthetic Judgement* (New Brunswick and London: Transaction Publishers, 2006).

Realitatea ilustrata, 1929-1937.

Rîpeanu, Bujor T., *Filmul documentar. 1897-1948 (The Documentary Film. 1897-1948)* (București: Meronia, 2008).

Silureanu, N. (University Professor), ‘Ce-or mai fi făcând Miss-ele?’ (‘What Are the Beauty queens Up to These Days?’), *Cultura Poporului (The People’s Culture)*, Bucharest, IX. 293 (29 September 1929): 1.

‘A fugit de la părinți o frumusețe de fată’ (‘Looker Runs Away From Her Parents’, in ‘Știrile săptămânale’ (‘Weekly News’), *Unirea poporului (The People’s Unification)*, Blaj, 3 (19 January 1930): 5-6.

Notes

ⁱ In order to qualify to the Miss Romania – Miss Universe pageant, the candidates had to be between 16 and 25 years old, unmarried, to live with their parents or earn their wages in honest work. The ones interested had to complete a form with their name, address, profession, type of accommodation (with the parents, alone, or with a relative), age, height, waist, hair colour, and weight along with a recent picture.

ⁱⁱ See Cohen Ballerino, C. Richard Wilk and Beverly Stoeltje, Introduction to *Queens on the Global Stage: Gender, Contests and Power*, eds. Cohen Ballerino, C. Richard Wilk and Beverly Stoeltje (New York and London: Routledge, 1996), 2.

ⁱⁱⁱ Ibid.

^{iv} Arthur Marwick, *It. A History of Human Beauty*. (London and New York: Hambledon and London, 2004), 7.

^v See Stoeltje, ‘The Snake Charmer Queen: Ritual, Competition and Signification in American Festival’, in Ballerino, Wilk and Stoeltje, *Beauty Queens on the Global Stage*, 15.

^{vi} Ballerino, Wilk and Stoeltje, Introduction to *Queens on the Global Stage: Gender*, 10.

^{vii} Not to be confused with the homonymous weekly magazine published between June and December 1891 or the bi-monthly captioned *Artistic, Literary, Illustrated Magazine* that only lasted for two issues in 1903.

^{viii} *Ilustrațiunea Română* was a weekly supplement of the *Universul –The Universe newspaper* (See *Ilustrațiunea Română* II. 45 (30 October 1930) for a detailed view about the *Universul* newspaper and images from *Universul* palace). The newspaper was published between 1929 and 1939. It was a complex source for both illustrated news, images from all over the world and cultural, scientific and humorous articles. See I. Hangiu, *Dicționarul presei literare românești. 1790-1990 (The Dictionary of Romanian Literary Press. 1790-1990)* (Bucharest: Editura Fundației Culturale Române, 1996), 237.

^{ix} Its competitor, *Realitatea Ilustrată*, captioned *The Things as We See Them With Our Eyes* was published between 1927 and 1940 in Cluj-Napoca, 1940-1946 and 1949 and would include a short-lived supplement entitled *Reportaj (Reportage)*

captioned *The Magazine of Sensational Facts* in 1931. See Hangiu. *Dicționarul presei literare românești*, 540.

^x See <http://www.prewarcar.com/magazine/previous-features/a-brand-new-ford-v8-for-miss-romania-016819.html> Last accessed 29 August 2013.

^{xi} See http://www.pageantopolis.com/Int_past/europe_1929-1938.htm Last accessed 29 August 2013.

^{xii} Ballerino, Wilk and Stoeltje, Introduction to *Queens on the Global Stage*, 8.

^{xiii} *Realitatea Ilustrată* III. 30 (20 July 1929): 12-13.

^{xiv} Stoeltje, “The Snake Charmer Queen”, 14-15.

^{xv} ‘Alegerea „Miss România”’. Grandioasa manifestație pentru „Miss Arad”’ (‘The Election of Miss Romania.’ The Grand Manifestation for “Miss Arad”), *Românul – Organ al Partidului Național Țărănesc Român Arad (The Romanian – Agency of the Romanian National Peasants’ Party Arad)*, Arad, 13 (24 March 1929): 2.

^{xvi} Also a high-profiled member of the National Peasants’ Party.

^{xvii} *Realitatea Ilustrată* III. 30 (20 July 1929), 7 September 1929. Apart from the business element that was not entirely covert, Goldarbeiter was very well received, with huge crowds, sumptuous events and many photographic smiles. The two beauty queens travelled chaperoned by their mothers and were always accompanied by a various officials, reporters, movie makers and fans. By visiting certain department stores or institutions followed by this gargantuan entourage, they became the perfect tool to ensure a business boom incongruous to the contemporary Great Depression.

^{xviii} *Ilustrațiunea Română* II. 1(1 January 1930): 15.

^{xix} Roughly 19,500 dollars, currently around 280,000 dollars today.

^{xx} ‘De vorbă cu Domnișoara Zoica Dona, Miss Romania 1930’ (‘A Conversation with Miss Zoica Dona, Miss Romania 1930’), *Ilustrațiunea Română* II. 1 (1 January 1930): 4-5, 9.

^{xxi} ‘Dela concursul nostrum de frumusețe’ (‘From Our Beauty Contest’), *Ibid.*, 10-11.

^{xxii} ,“Miss România” – d-ra Zoica Dona – pe Coasta de Azur’ („Miss Romania” – Miss Zoica Dona – On the Cote d’Azur’), *Ibid.*, 9.

^{xxiii} Ion Golea, ‘Sărbătoarea dela Sinaia’ (The Sinaia Feast) *Realitatea Ilustrată*, IV. 161 (27 February 1930): 13, 16.

^{xxiv} ‘Un caleidoscop al concursului de frumusețe de la Sinaia’ (‘A Kaleidoscope of the Sinaia Beauty Contest’), *Ibid.*, 14-15.

^{xxv} *Ilustrațiunea Română* II. 10 (27 February 1930).

^{xxvi} *Ibid.*, 2.

^{xxvii} *Realitatea Ilustrată* IV. 162 (6 March 1930): 7, 10.

^{xxviii} *Ilustrațiunea Română* III. 5 (29 January 1931).

^{xxix} ,Marele concurs național de frumusețe organizat de revista noastră – D-ra Tanți Viișoreanu a fost proclamată Miss România 1931’ (‘The Great Beauty Contest Organized By Our Magazine – Miss Tanți Viișoreanu Was Proclaimed Miss Romania 1931’), *Ibid.*, 9.

^{xxx} ‘Alegerea Miss României’ (‘Choosing Miss Romania’), *Ibid.*, 10-11.

^{xxxi} *Ibid.*; also see: ‘Ce mi-a povestit Miss România 1931’ (‘What Miss Romania 1931 Told Me’), *Ilustrațiunea Română*, III. 6 (5 February 1931): 9, 12.

^{xxxii} ‘“Miss România 1931” A Fost Aleasă. D-ra Erastia Peretz a fost aleasă “Miss România 1931”. Noua aleasă – O îndrăgostită de natură și de muzică. “Tia” în intimidat. – între literatură și Universitate’ (““Miss Romania 1931” Was Elected. Miss Erastia Peretz was elected “Miss Romania 1931.” The newly chosen – A lover of nature and music. “Tia” in private. – Between literature and the University’), *Realitatea Ilustrată*, V. 228 (11 June 1931): 5-6.

^{xxxiii} *Realitatea Ilustrată*, V. 228 (11 June 1931): 5, 6. The article also mentions the runner up, Elena Mischiu, who was also Miss Oltenia in 1930. The third place was won by Păpușa Vlasiu, former Miss Ardeal 1930. The piece includes two studio portraits of Peretz (one in a popular costume) and a studio portrait of Elena Mischiu, also in popular costume.

^{xxxiv} *Ilustrațiunea Română* V. 20 (10 May 1933).

^{xxxv} Ion Tic, ‘Alegerea „Miss României” 1933 – Note, impresii, spovedanii’ (‘The Election of “Miss Romania” 1933 – Notes, Impressions, Confessions’), *Ibid.*, 6-7.

^{xxxvi} *Ibid.*, 7.

^{xxxvii} Tic, ‘Alegerea „Miss României”, *Ilustrațiunea Română*, V. 20 (10 May 1933): 6-7.

^{xxxviii} Beauty contests were consistently echoed in Romanian Interwar literature, press and cinema. See Bujor T. Rîpeanu, *Filmul documentar. 1897-1948 (The Documentary Film. 1897-1948)* (București: Meronia, 2008): ‘Concursul de frumusețe de la ștrand’ (‘Beach Beauty Contest’), 27 August 1929 (premiere, Capitol movie theatre; reportage, ‘Miss Univers, Miss Egipt, Miss România și concursul de frumusețe de la Ștrand’ – ‘Miss Universe, Miss Egypt, Miss Romania and the Beach beauty contest’, *Universul*, 23, 24, 27, 28-31 August; 1, 2, 4-6 September 1929, *Dimineața*, 27, 29 August 1929), 254; ‘Concursul național de frumusețe al ziarului ‘Universul’ (‘The National Beauty Contest of the ‘Universul’ Newspaper’), Palatul Universul, 1 January 1929 (premiere, Trianon and Odeon movie theatres, *Universul*, 16-18 January 1929, *Dimineața*, 14 January 1929), 254-255; ‘Cu Miss Univers la Ștrand’ (‘With Miss Universe on the Beach’), 3 March 1929 (premiere, Capitol movie theatre, *Universul*, 3 September 1929, *Dimineața*, 3 September 1929), 255; ‘Miss România’, 20 March 1929 (premiere, Capitol and Trianon movie theatres; reportage, ‘Alegerea domnișoarei Magda Demetrescu, Miss România’ – ‘The Election of miss Magda Demetrescu, Miss Romania’, *Universul*, 17 19-23 March 1929, *Dimineața*, 17, 21 March, 29 August 1929, *Cinema*, 109, 1929), 261; ‘Miss Univers la Sinaia’ (‘Miss Universe in Sinaia’), 31 August 1929 (premiere, Capitol movie theatre, *Universul*, 31 August 1929), 262; ‘Concurs de frumusețe pentru alegerea de Miss România, 1930’ (‘Beauty Contest for the Election of Miss Romania, 1930’, *Realitatea ilustrată*, 24 April 1930), 274; ‘Concurs de frumusețe la Sinaia’ (‘Beauty Contest in Sinaia’), 27 February 1930 (premiere Capitol movie theatre, *Rampa*, 21-28 February 1930), 274-275.

^{xxxix} I. Doru, *Regină pentru un an. Romanul unui concurs de frumusețe – Miss Romania – Miss Universe (Queen for a Year. The Novel of a Beauty Contest – Miss Romania – Miss Universe)* (Bucharest: N/A)

^{xl} Ballerino, Wilk and Stoeltje, Introduction to *Queens on the Global Stage: Gender*, 5-7.

^{xli} Constantin Noica, 'Literatura gen "Miss Romania"' ('Literature "Miss Romania" Style'), in Constantin Noica, *Semnele Minervei. Publicistica, I. 1927-1929 (The Signs of Minerva. Publishing, I. 1927-1929)* (Bucharest: Humanitas, 1994), 206.

^{xlii} Noica, 'Miss Romania' literaturizeaza' ('"Miss Romania" Literaturizes') in Noica, *Semnele Minervei*, 221-222

^{xliii} Cezar Petrescu, 'Miss Romania', in Cezar Petrescu, *La paradis general - Miss Romania (At General Paradise - Miss Romania)* (second edition, Bucharest: Cartea Romaneasca, 1970), 287-537.

^{xliv} See : M.A. 'Epilogul concursului de frumusețe mondial. Frumusețea feminină ca mijloc de speculă; d-ra Goldarbeiter se arată pentru bani' (,The Epilogue of the World Beauty Contest. Female Beauty as a Means of Profit; Miss Goldarbeiter Shows Up For Money'), *Clujul* 29-35 (8 September 1929): 1.

^{xlv} Brenda Foley, *Undressed for Success. Beauty Contestants and Exotic Dancers as Merchants of Morality* (New York and Basingstoke, Hampsire: PalgraveMacmillan, 2005), 1.

^{xlvi} 'Știri' ('News'), *Foaia diecezana. Organul eparhiei ortodoxe romane a Caransebeșului (The Diocesan Paper. The Organ of the Orthodox Diocese of Caransebeș)* 6 (7 February 1932): 7.

^{xlvii} Sarah Banet-Weiser, *The Most Beautiful Girl in the World. Beauty Pageants and National Identity* (Berkeley, Los Angeles and London: University of California Press, 1999), 210.